

Kinetics and Mechanism of Hydrolysis of 2-Methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium Iodide

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Kinetic runs with 2-methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (3) in 50% methanol ($\mu = 0.05$) indicated that the rate constant (k_{ob}) of the hydrolysis of 3 is practically pH independent at $\text{pH} > 4$ with first order dependence on [substrate]. Partial inhibition of the hydrolysis at $\text{pH} < 4$ and the negative salt effect are attributed to specific cation-anion interaction. Hydrolysis of 3 is also subject to general base catalysis with Brønsted constant $\beta \approx 0.2$. Increase in rate with decreasing polarity of the medium and the small magnitude of $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are consistent with unimolecular breakdown of a nonpolar intermediate. Probable course of the degradation of 3 has been discussed in the light of experimental data.

It was reported¹ earlier that 2-methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (3) is an excellent intermediate for the conversion of mesoionic 1,3,4-thiadiazole systems (1) to mesoionic *s*-triazole systems (2) by treatment of 3 with primary amines. While the reaction was quite smooth with aliphatic amines, reaction products from aromatic amines were frequently contaminated with *N*-benzoyl-*N*-phenyl-dithiocarbamate (4), and sometimes, it was the sole product of reaction¹. Evidently, 3 is very prone to hydrolysis, and this prompted us to examine the hydrolytic behaviour of 3 under more well defined conditions, and the relevant data are presented in this communication

used, and the reaction was essentially neutral in character.

Unless otherwise indicated ionic strengths were always adjusted with KCl, and the kinetic runs were followed by spectrophotometric technique in 50% v/v methanol at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.05$).

Kinetic measurements: Experiments were carried out in stoppered volumetric flasks at $40^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ or at lower temperature depending on the temperature desired, and the solutions were always freshly prepared. Other details were the same as before². Trial runs indicated a regular loss in intensity of the long

Experimental

Materials: The required compound (3) was prepared by the reported¹ method and was repeatedly crystallised from acetone as yellow crystals, m.p. $185^\circ\text{-}86^\circ$. Solvents (methanol and 95% ethanol) and all other reagents were as described earlier². In the acidic region HCl and KCl mixtures as well as acetate buffers were used for adjusting pH, and dilute NaOH and KCl mixtures were used under alkaline condition. In all cases pH values (± 0.05) of appropriate blanks and the sample solutions were checked with Cambridge pH meter at *ca* 25° . Maintenance of pH during the kinetic runs presented no problem as dilute solutions ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-4} M$) of the substrate were

used, and the reaction was essentially neutral in character. Kinetic runs were therefore followed under pseudo first order condition at wave lengths appropriate to experimental condition against suitable reagent blanks. Runs were normally followed until the fall in absorbance values (A_t) were at least 80% or more of the initial values. Decomposition product(s) did not interfere with runs; however, small absorbance values (A_∞) were consistently noted at the end of the kinetic runs. Rates were therefore calculated from the first order plots of $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs time (sec), and the plots in all cases complied with first order kinetics. Rate constants were estimated to be better than $\pm 3\%$ by agreement between duplicate

experiments, and were corrected to zero buffer concentration.

Apparent second order buffer catalytic constants (k_B) were calculated from the slopes of the linear plots of $(k_{ob} - k_0)$ vs $[\text{buffer}]_T$ at several different buffer ratios where $k_0 = k_{ob}$ ($0.8622 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) in 50% methanol (water reaction) in the absence of any added salt or buffer. As the points provided a single intercept at three different pH values, catalysis by acidic species were excluded from our consideration. The corresponding second order buffer catalytic constant (k_2) were then derived either from the ordinate intercept of the plots of k_B against percentage free base in various buffers or simply by dividing k_B with % free base in the given buffer³.

It is to be noted that pK_a values of the conjugate acids in Fig. 2 are those in water at 25°. This is justified by assuming small and parallel changes in pK_a for structurally similar acids under consideration in going from water to 50% methanol⁴. Further, use of rate data and pK_a values at two different temperatures in Brønsted plots have been used with fair success⁵.

Solvent effects were ascertained under neutral condition in the absence of any added salt or buffer. Activation parameters were calculated at 50% and 80% methanol contents in the medium with standard equations using $\log k_{ob}$ vs T^{-1} and are based on rate constants measured at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40°. Estimated precision in ΔS^* is ± 1 e.u., and in all other cases it is around ca 0.5 Kcal M^{-1} .

Product analysis: Absorption spectra of the authentic sample of 4 in 50% methanol at pH 4.55, 7.0 and 10.1 were practically superimposable with the absorption pattern of the decomposition product(s) of 3 under similar experimental condition. It clearly shows the formation of the same product (4) under all circumstances, and are also in agreement with the *tlc* monitored data after the kinetic runs.

Results and Discussions

pH-rate profile: The apparent first order rate constants for the hydrolysis of 3 are presented in table 1. At constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.05$) and solvent composition (50% methanol), rate constants are practically pH independent with $k_{ob} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, and it decreases marginally at $\text{pH} < 4$. But there was no detectable decomposition of 3 in the presence of 1.5M and 3.0M HCl. The extent of this inhibition is ca 22% only between pH 1 and 4 despite nearly 1000 fold changes in hydronium ion concentration. This is difficult to understand in terms of an effect on the activity of water, hence the observed rate reduction under acidic condition is assumed to reflect a change in the activity of the reactive species due to cation-anion interaction, and that probably explains complete suppression of hydrolysis of 3 under strongly acidic condition. A striking example of an analogous situation is found with the reported⁶ kinetic behaviour of acetyl imidazolium cation.

TABLE I. APPARENT FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{ob}) UNDER VARIOUS EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS (T = 40°; Solvent = 50% v/v methanol).

No.	Experimental pH	Ionic strength (μ)	Rate constants $10^4 k_{ob}, \text{sec}^{-1}$	Measured at <i>nm</i>
1	1.50	0.05	0.7766	325
2	1.85	"	0.7766	"
3	4.08	"	0.8800	"
4	4.90	"	0.8800	"
5	5.40	"	1.057	"
6	5.70	"	0.9300	"
7	6.18	"	1.053	"
8	6.80	"	1.066	"
9	7.50	"	1.105	298
10	8.25	"	0.9350	"
11	9.60	"	1.087	"
12	10.90	"	0.9475	"
13	12.30	"	1.247	"
14	7.00	0.20	0.7787	325
15	7.00	0.60	0.7818	"
16	7.00	0.80	0.7544	"
17	7.00	1.00	0.6190	"
18	7.00	1.00(Br)	0.4652	"
19	7.00	1.00(KI)	0.2666	"

The above results show that hydrolysis apparently proceeds *via* water attack on 3 at C-5 in agreement with the structure of the decomposition product (4). As the substrate is likely to dissociate, at least in part, under the experimental condition, participation of the solvated cation(s) could be reasonably assumed in the course of the above reaction. Analogous water catalysed reactions have been observed previously on many occasions, such as, hydrolysis of 2-(4-nitrophenoxy)-tetrahydropyran⁷ and benzaldehyde methyl *s*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl) thioacetal⁸. Data presented here, however, are in sharp contrast with specific hydroxyl ion catalysed decomposition of 1 under alkaline condition².

Buffer effect: Buffer catalysis was examined with buffers composed of four different carboxylic acids and their salts (Table 2). Data thus generated by several fold variation in buffer concentration clearly indicate (Fig. 1) increasing slope of k_{ob} vs $[\text{buffer}]_T$ with increasing pH of the medium, and the rates were also found to increase (Table 2) with increasing concentration of the buffer base at constant pH and ionic strength ($\mu = 1.0$). Plots also revealed a single intercept at three different pH values as well as zero intercept at 0% base which confirms the absence of any detectable catalysis by acidic species of the buffers. We therefore infer that water addition to 3 is indeed subject to general base catalysis only⁹.

The above results are also presented as Brønsted plot in Fig. 2. But the point for water ($pK_a, -1.74$), the calculated bimolecular rate constant ($0.2230 \times 10^{-5} M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) in 50% methanol ($\mu = 1.0$) lies several log units below the line established by Brønsted plot ($\beta \cong 0.2$). Deviations of this kind with water or hydroxyl ion as reactant are not uncommon. For instance, in the base catalysed addition of bisulphite to 1,3-dimethyl uracil, the second order rate

TABLE 2. BUFFER EFFECT ON OBSERVED RATES (k_{ob})
(Solvent = 50% v/v MeOH; T = 40°; $\mu = 1.0 M$)

Buffer species	pKa	pH	Total (Buffer) [M]	Buffer Base (M)	$10^4 k_{ob}$ in sec ⁻¹	$10^4 k_B$ M ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$10^4 k_2$ M ⁻¹ sec
Chloroacetate	2.8	3.50	0.146	0.05	0.7231	0.7408	2.163
			0.292	0.10	0.7818		
			0.584	0.20	0.8698		
			0.730	0.25	1.105		
Formate	3.77	4.10	0.138	0.0428	0.7463	0.8636	2.781
			0.276	0.0856	0.8345		
			0.552	0.1712	1.016		
			0.690	0.2142	1.199		
Phenyl-acetate†	4.31	5.20	0.09	0.0214	0.8724	2.222	5.607‡
			0.18	0.0428	1.0660		
			0.36	0.0856	1.3910		
			0.45	0.1070	1.6630		
Acetate	4.76	5.70	0.20	0.16	1.279	3.00	3.750
			0.40	0.32	1.751		
			0.80	0.64	2.878		
		4.90	0.20	0.06	0.8395	1.428	
			0.60	0.18	1.535		
			1.0	0.30	2.132		
		4.08	0.20	0.01	0.7196	0.3076	
			0.60	0.03	0.8529		
			1.0	0.05	1.010		

† Data based on experiments at $\mu = 0.5$

‡ Corrected to $\mu = 1.0$ by ca 40% rate reduction based on Salt effect (IM).

constant for the hydroxyl ion catalysed reaction is about 200 fold less than that predicted by the amine data¹⁰. But the size of the Brønsted slope is undoubtedly small and it possibly indicates a poor proton transfer in the rate determining step. Com-

instance could be detected only because of the absence of any catalytic activity of the hydroxyl ion.

Salt effect: The effect of raising the ionic strength of the medium under neutral condition is presented in Table 1. It is clear from data that the salt exerts a negative effect on the rate, and it increases with increasing amount of salt in the medium. Plots of $\log k_{ob}$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ or μ show good linearity as required by Debye-Huckel equations¹⁴, but the magnitude of the negative slope is extremely poor. This slight negative effect is in contrast with theory¹⁴ which predicts a slight positive salt effect when a neutral molecule and an ion are involved in the transition state. In the light of unimolecular decomposition of 3, the results recorded here therefore reflect a secondary effect due to reduced cativity of the action involved in the transition state. In other words, the reaction must proceed *via* the thiadiazolium cation from 3. This is consistent with the observed inhibition of hydrolysis under strongly acidic condition.

The above contention is also supported by data on the effect of KCl, KBr and KI (1.0M in each) on the reaction rates. The observed sequence of inhibition and their relative efficiency in suppressing the rates are as follows: Cl (38%), Br (54%) and I (73%). This is also entirely consistent with the known order of softness¹⁵ of the halides, and indirectly suggests some stabilisation of the thiadiazolium cation through charge dispersion.

Solvent and temperature effect: Sensitivity of the reaction to the composition of the solvent are presented

Fig. 1. Dependence of k_{ob} of buffer concentration (acetate) at three different pH values.

parable values of β have been reported earlier, such as reactions of *p*-nitrophenyl phosphate dianion with amines ($\beta \cong 0.13$)¹¹, reactions of pyridines with ethyl methane sulphonate ($\beta \cong 0.11$)¹² and the hydrolysis of ethyl trifluorothiolacetate ($\beta \cong 0.2$)¹³. It thus appears that the observed general base catalysis in the given

Fig. 2. Brønsted plot of $\log k_2$ against pK_a of the conjugate acids of the buffer bases.

in Table 3 with pertinent data on activation parameters. There was no measurable rate of hydrolysis in pure methanol. Extrapolation of data for methanol and ethanol in Table 3 provided a single intercept with $k_{ob} = 0.1405 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in 100% water compared to a value of $k_{ob} = 0.8622 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in 50% methanol. Further, plots of $\log k_{ob}$ vs $1/D$ show good linearity with a positive slope where D is the bulk dielectric constant of the medium. Excellent linearity is also found by the use of Winstein-Grunwald Y parameter¹⁶. These results clearly show that as the dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate of reaction also increases. This is what is expected¹⁴ of a reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule like water, and indirectly confirms the formation of a neutral intermediate in the rate determining step.

Evidence in support of the above contention is also found with the activation parameters shown in Table 3. Thus, involvement of water in a rate determining step should give highly negative entropy of activation (ΔS^*), but the observed values of ΔS^* in 50% (-2.2 e.u.) and 80% (+4.6 e.u.) methanol are typically¹⁷ those found with unimolecular reactions. Observed solvent effect then reflects increasing desolvation of the solvated cation with increasing proportion of the organic cosolvent, and the resulting

favourable entropic changes ($\delta\Delta S^*$) must be one of the prime reasons for the rate acceleration.

This is probably true as long as the solvation core of the cation is relatively undisturbed. For instance the entire body of data (Table 3) could not be reconciled with polarity factor alone. Linearity always breaks down at ca 80% methanol or 90% ethanol content in the medium corresponding to ca 0.36 mole fraction of water (Fig.3). Inhibition of rate is observed with further increase in the proportion of the organic cosolvent, and the relative rate ratio at the maxima, k_{ob} (90% ethanol)/ k_{ob} (80% methanol) is ca 2.7 despite isodielectric nature of the related solvents at the maxima. Observed rate maxima then probably indicates the extreme points where this solvation shell is not seriously disrupted. The region beyond these points therefore represents region of gross structural rearrangement in the solvation shell which inhibits specific solvation necessary for the progress of the reaction. This is supported by the absence of any reaction in pure methanol. Similar situation with changing water concentration of the medium has been previously observed on numerous occasions^{18,19}, and the recently reported²⁰ kinetic behaviour of 7-methyl-7-norbornyl tosylate in trifluoroethanol is a typical case,

TABLE 3 SOLVENT AND TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON RATE UNDER NEUTRAL CONDITION AND $\mu = 0$

Methanol		Ethanol		Activation parameter [†]
% (v/v)	$10^4 k_{ob}$, sec ⁻¹ at 40°	% (v/v)	$10^4 k_{ob}$, sec ⁻¹ at 40°	
10	0.2924	9.5	0.2559	E_A 25° (Kcal/mole) =
30	0.4021	28.5	0.6159	24.08 (50% MeOH) &
50	0.8622	47.5	1.0640	22.88 (80% MeOH)
70	1.3710	66.5	2.860	ΔG^* (Kcal/mole) =
80	1.956	80.75	4.0130	24.17 (50% MeOH) &
90	1.326	90.0	5.330	20.80 (80% MeOH)
95	0.8529	95.0	3.721	ΔS^* (e.u. = -2.28 (50% MeOH) & +4.56 (80% MeOH)

[†] ΔG^* and ΔS^* were calculated at 40° and are based on rate data obtained at 25°, 30°, 35° and 40°

